

STUDY, DISTRIBUTION AND METHODS OF BREAST CANCER RESEARCH IN DOGS IN UZBEKISTAN

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The role of cynologists and service dogs in the military structures of the countries of the world is incomparable. In particular, dogs of different breeds are used to fight crime and prevent the penetration of drugs, weapons and explosives from other countries into the territory of the republic. However, as the number of service dogs increases, they are diagnosed with various infectious, non-infectious and parasitic diseases that worsen their health. Breast cancer is particularly common in dogs, accounting for 5 to 10 percent of all cases.

A number of measures are being taken around the world to diagnose, treat and prevent cancer in dogs. In particular, much attention is paid to the prevention and treatment of canine service dogs, dogs serving private veterinary clinics, dogs of

ABSTRACT

This article describes the spread, prevention and treatment of breast cancer in dogs of different breeds kept in canine kennels in Uzbekistan, the level and methods of research of this disease.

various breeds bred at home. Early detection, treatment, and control of cancer in dogs is also important.

During the years of independence of the republic, modern advanced methods for diagnosing and preventing various etiological diseases of service dogs and home-breeding dogs have been introduced. The use of drugs has significantly reduced the incidence of infectious and non-infectious pathologies. Treatment of oncological diseases of service dogs of military structures and the population of our country and acceleration of research on preventive measures.

On a global scale, this problem was solved by a number of foreign scientists J.C. Costa, P. Juntas, M. Pogacnik, B. Lamagna, P. A. Le Couteur, A. J. Withrow, G. C. Leonardi, S. .L.Guerra, A.Monteros, N.Milla, J.B.Paul,

M.K.Jose, S.Bunchop, A.Polli, P.F.Tereksov, V.N.Ellinidi, M.V.Sheleksova, A.A. Samotaev, V.I. Chissov, V.V. Starinsky, E.A. Ulriks, E.L. Neishtadt, V.M. Moiseenko, A.V. Geinis, S.V. Moskvina, G.A. Azizov studied the distribution, pathomorphology, clinical signs of tumors in dogs and developed evidence-based measures for the treatment and prevention of the disease. B.D. Narziev on the spread of tumors in dogs in our country, their treatment Tashtemirov R.M., Yulchiev Zh.B. on their treatment and prevention, as well as its implementation.

Object and subject of research. In 2021-2022, it was held in the private veterinary clinic "Darel" in the Mirzo-Ulugbek district of Tashkent in dogs of different ages and breeds with a diagnosis of breast cancer.

Research methods: The following methods were used in the experiments.

1. Collection of anamnestic data. Information is obtained from the owner of the sick animal or the person caring for it. It basically determines the following: the conditions of keeping, feeding and exploitation of the animal, when the tumor appeared, its quantity, growth rate, and the negative impact on the body of the animal that provided assistance.

2. Method of palpation. Local temperature, pain in the tissues surrounding the tumor, the state of the tissues formed in the tumor layer, the sounds of fluctuation and crepitus, the state of the lymph nodes, the presence of metastases.

3. Puncture method. mainly used for differential diagnosis. Since tumors must be differentiated from hematomas, lymphatic extravasations and tumors. The hematoma bleeds, and the lymphoextravasation contains a yellow fluid

sac, an opening, and organs protruding into it.

4. The cytological method is a relatively simple, inexpensive, fast method. In this case, a certain number of cells are taken from the tumor. Examined under a microscope.

5. Histological method - the tumor removed during the operation is sent to the pathology laboratory. They conduct a histological examination to determine the type of tumor and make a diagnosis.

6. Ultrasound examination gives very good results. Today this method is widely used.

The results obtained. Although the importance of tumor pathology in animals is incomparable with human pathology, the problem of malignant tumors is still relevant in veterinary medicine. In recent years, the number of tumors in dogs living in large cities has been increasing, causing concern and causing significant damage to the health of dogs. Various methods are used to treat tumors, including conservative (chemotherapeutic), radiation and surgical (surgical) methods. Tumors are usually treated with surgery in human and veterinary medicine. Tumors in the pathology of the dog's body are theoretical and are a complex problem in applied veterinary medicine. Therefore, the fight against cancer is an urgent task for veterinarians. The overall effect of tumors on the animal's body also depends on the location of the tumor and its quality. If the tumor has grown around or in a vital organ, its effects on the animal can be even more dangerous. It is also important to have a high rate of tumor growth. The pathogenesis of tumors is also complex, for example, one of the hypotheses of cancer

pathogenesis is that the cell membrane and the internal components of oncooxyls 10 bind to each other, stopping the differentiation of proliferating cells, acting together, modifying (modifying) receptors), cells lose sensitivity to corrective (controlling)) influences, change the spectrum of surface antigens, and as a result, a normal cell becomes mutant.

Conclusions. According to the literature, the development of tumors by stage 3-4 begins the process of decay, starting from the center of the tissue in

which it is formed. As a result, toxins begin to accumulate there and be absorbed into the body, disrupting the functioning of all organs and systems, including nonspecific defenses, and having a significant negative impact on the immune system. This weakens the body's ability to defend itself and leads to the multiplication of tumor cells. Therefore, we set ourselves the goal of studying the effect of dog tumors on the immune system and determining changes in immunological parameters.

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